

**RAPID REVIEW PROTOCOL:
Technology Probe of Software Technologies
May - 2024 (Updated on June 2026)**

1. Scenario

Technology Probe (TP) is a collaborative method between users and developers to create new technologies. This method requires a Probe (functional prototype) to be installed in the user's environment, allowing the developers to collect their perceptions and improve the Probe. These collected data are evaluated regarding three aspects [Hutchinson et al. 2003]: (i) social, focusing on user interaction with the probe; (ii) engineer, focusing on the technology or manufacturing; (iii) design, identifying opportunities for innovation.

Even though TP seems a promising method to co-create technologies and evaluate software from a user perspective, it has a complication in its applicability. To use Technology Probe, the researcher must develop a technique, such as defining instruments to collect and analyse data. This research aims to map TP techniques developed in other studies. This way, it is possible to understand this field's state of the art and propose a unified approach for TP.

2. Goal and Research Question

a. Goal

The main goal of this research is to understand how studies used the Technology Probe method in order to identify techniques and instruments employed for the TP.

b. Problem

There is no standard for applying Technology Probe. The researcher is responsible for developing a technique for using it (participant/user profile, instruments to collect and analyse data..., etc.). Therefore, organising the knowledge regarding which TP techniques have already been developed and used is relevant for the evolution of this method.

c. Research Questions:

How is Technology Probe being used to evaluate software technologies?

What techniques or practices can be used to support the Technology Probe in software engineering?

3. Sources, Language e Research String

a. Source

This study will use the Scopus database, which integrates different libraries and provides diverse results from peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference proceedings. There will be two research strings applied in Scopus, both following the PICOC structure. One more general to and another restricting the context to participatory design, since it is an often-used term within the TP field and therefore it is interesting to to assess the

assess the coverage of the term in the original research string. Additionally, the snowballing (one step forward/backward) will be performed using the final selected papers that were published after 2020, to ensure the identification of recent developments in the field while keeping the process feasible within the Rapid Review methodology.

b. Language and Research String

The language chosen for the selection of work is "English". Regarding the search string, the expression was defined using the PICOC method [Petticrew & Roberts, 2006].

PICOC	STRING
<i>Population</i>	("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "MVP" OR "Minimum Viable Product" OR "technolog*") AND
<i>Intervention</i>	("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND
<i>Comparison</i>	-
<i>Outcome</i>	("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study")
<i>Context</i>	-

The Scopus search string is: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "mvp" OR "minimum viable product" OR "technolog*") AND ("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND ("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

PICOC	STRING
<i>Population</i>	("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "MVP" OR "Minimum Viable Product" OR "technolog*") AND
<i>Intervention</i>	("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND
<i>Comparison</i>	-
<i>Outcome</i>	("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study")
<i>Context</i>	"participatory design"

The Scopus search string is: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "mvp" OR "minimum viable product" OR "technolog*") AND ("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND ("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study") AND ("participatory design")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

4. Criteria

a. Inclusion Criteria

- To discuss a Technology Probe technique
- It is related to software technologies
- Peer-reviewed English text
- It is a primary study

b. Exclusion Criteria

- Full text is not available;
- Duplicated studies;
- It is a secondary study (e.g., another rapid review);
- Do not discuss a TP technique; only replicate one (use snowballing to get the work that proposes the technique)
- Chapter Books and reviews

5. Data Extraction

a. Extraction model

A) Papers Data:	
Title:	work title
Author(s):	authors name
Source:	Where it was published
Year:	publication year
Abstract:	work abstract
Problem domain:	domain of technology that is being proposed
B) Data based on the Goal:	
Motivation	motivation to use technology probe
Probe	what was the software technology solution used
Technique	description of the technique or practice proposed in the work
Outcomes	conclusions from the Technology Probe
Advantages of the Technique (optional)	what were the advantages of using the described technique
Disadvantages of the Technique (optional)	what were the disadvantages of using the described technique

b. Extracted data from the Selected Papers: [Google Spreadsheet](#)

6. Update

a. (December/24)

On 18/December/24 the search was done again. It returned 287 documents (having 24 extra papers). These papers will be submitted to the same filter that the other ones had

b. (February/26)

On 04/February/26 the search was done again. It returned 59 extra papers. These papers will be submitted to the same filter that the other ones had

c. (June/26)

On 09/June/26, the search was conducted using the term "participatory design" as the context for the PICOCE. It returned 33 papers, but after checking duplicates against previous iterations, only 4 extra papers were identified. These papers will be submitted to the same filter as the other searches.

Also, to complement the search, one stage of the snowballing (forward, through Google Scholar, and backward by the list of references). For that, the selected articles published after 2020 will be analyzed in order to focus on recent research. The following is the list of papers that were used in the snowballing:

1. Designing Digital Safe Spaces for Peer Support and Connectivity in Patriarchal Contexts
2. Exploring the Opportunities of AR for Enriching Storytelling with Family Photos between Grandparents and Grandchildren
3. Designing Mobile Health Applications to Support Walking for Older Adults
4. Probing IoT-based consumer services: ‘insights’ from the connected shower
5. More than step count: designing a workplace-based activity tracking system
6. The Patient Advice System: A Technology Probe Study to Enable Peer Support in the Hospital
7. Textlets: Supporting Constraints and Consistency in Text Documents
8. PowerCut and obfuscator: An exploration of the design space for privacy-preserving interventions for smart speakers
9. Co-designing a Technology Probe with Experienced Designers
10. Introducing and Familiarising Older Adults Living with Dementia and Their Caregivers to Virtual Reality
11. Model LineUpper: Supporting Interactive Model Comparison at Multiple Levels for AutoML
12. Here and Now: Creating Improvisational Dance Movements with a Mixed Reality Mirror
13. Mixed Reality Musical Interface: Exploring Ergonomics and Adaptive Hand Pose Recognition for Gestural Control
14. Exploring Embodied Approaches for Large Age Gap Sibling Communication through Technology Probes
15. Understanding individuals with spinal cord injury’s self-care practices: a technology probe study to promote pressure relief adherence
16. WovenProbe: Probing Possibilities for Weaving Fully-Integrated On-Skin Systems Deployable in the Field
17. Pearl: A Technology Probe for Machine-Assisted Reflection on Personal Data
18. NkhukuProbe: Using a Sensor-Based Technology Probe to Support Poultry Farming Activities in Malawi
19. Practice-informed Patterns for Organizing Large Groups in Distributed Mixed Reality Collaboration
20. “This really lets us see the entire world:” Designing a conversational telepresence robot for homebound older adults
21. From Awareness to Action: Exploring End-User Empowerment Interventions for Dark Patterns in UX
22. Expanding the Design Space of Computer Vision-based Interactive Systems for Group Dance Practice

23. Hapstick-Figure: Investigating the Design of a Haptic Representation of Human Gestures from Theater Performances for Blind and Visually-Impaired People
24. Are We on Track? AI-Assisted Active and Passive Goal Reflection during Meetings
25. Balancing Human Agency and AI Autonomy in Human-AI Idea Selection
26. Elmo: An Embodied Conversational Assistant For Community Repair Cafés
27. Hug Reports: Supporting Expression of Appreciation between Users and Contributors of Open Source Software Packages
28. Leveraging Usefulness and Autonomy: Designing AI-Mediated ASL Communication Between Hearing Parents and Deaf Children
29. Move with Me: Co-designing a Tangible User Interface to Promote Physical Activity among Rural South African Children
30. Orchid: A Creative Approach for Authoring LLM-Driven Interactive Narratives
31. Redesigning Fluid Tracking Probes for Elderly Lifestyle Retrofit
32. Reimagining Wearable-Based Digital Contact Tracing: Insights from Kenya and Côte d'Ivoire

7. References

Hutchinson, H., Mackay, W., Westerlund, B., Bederson, B. B., Druin, A., Plaisant, C., Beaudouin-Lafon, M., Conversy, S., Evans, H., Hansen, H., et al. (2003). Technology probes: inspiring design for and with families. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems, pages 17–24

Petticrew, Mark and Helen Roberts. *Systematic Reviews in the Social Sciences: A Practical Guide*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd, 2006, doi:10.1002/9780470754887.